

INNOVATION IN LANGUAGE TEACHING, LEARNING AND ASSESSMENT.

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***Annotatsiya:** Maqola yangi o'qitish usullarini o'rganish va joriy etishga bag'ishlangan. Bu tilni o'rganishda samaradorlik va faollikni oshiradigan innovatsion yondashuvlar va metodologiyalarga bo'lgan ehtiyojni ta'kidlaydi. Xususan, u istalgan vaqtda va istalgan joydan lingvistik materiallar va amaliy mashg'ulotlarga kirishni osonlashtiradigan onlayn platformalar, mobil ilovalar va interaktiv resurslar kabi texnologiyalarning rolini o'rganadi. Bundan tashqari, tadqiqot talabalar o'rtasida tanqidiy fikrlash va ijodkorlikni rivojlantirishga yordam beradigan loyihaga asoslangan ta'lim va amaliyotga yo'naltirilgan pedagogik strategiyalarning ahamiyatini ta'kidlaydi. Til kompetentsiyalarini baholash ham o'zgarmoqda; an'anaviy sinov usullari tobora moslashuvchan va xilma-xil baholash tizimlari, shu jumladan portfoliolar, o'z-o'zini baholash va shakllantiruvchi baholash bilan almashtirilmoqda. Ushbu zamonaviy yondashuvlar individual yutuqlar va o'quvchilar taraqqiyotini yanada aniqroq ko'rib chiqishga imkon beradi.*

***Kalit so'zlar:** tadqiqot, til, baholash tizimi, innovatsiya, rivojlanish, metodologiya, pedagogik strategiya, zamonaviy yondashuv, onlayn platforma.*

***Аннотация:** Статья посвящена исследованию и внедрению новых методов обучения. В ней подчеркивается необходимость инновационных подходов и методологии, которые повышают эффективность и вовлеченность в изучение языка. В частности, он исследует роль таких технологий, как онлайн-платформы, мобильные приложения и*

интерактивные ресурсы, которые облегчают доступ к лингвистическим материалам и практическим занятиям в любое время и из любого места. Кроме того, в исследовании подчеркивается важность проектного обучения и практико-ориентированных педагогических стратегий, которые помогают развивать критическое мышление и творчество среди студентов. Меняется и оценка языковых компетенций; традиционные методы тестирования заменяются все более гибкими и разнообразными системами оценки, включая портфолио, самооценку и формирующую оценку. Эти современные подходы более точно отражают индивидуальные достижения и прогресс учащихся.

Ключевые слова: *исследования, язык, система оценки, инновации, развитие, методология, педагогическая стратегия, современный подход, онлайн-платформа.*

Abstract: *The article is devoted to the research and implementation of new teaching methods. It highlights the need for innovative approaches and methodologies that increase efficiency and engagement in language learning. In particular, it studies the role of technologies such as online platforms, mobile applications and interactive resources that facilitate access to linguistic materials and practical activities at any time and from anywhere . Furthermore, the research emphasizes the significance of project-based learning and practice-oriented pedagogical strategies that foster the development of critical thinking and creativity among students. The assessment of language competencies is also undergoing a transformation; traditional testing methods are increasingly being supplanted by more flexible and diverse evaluative frameworks, including portfolios, self-assessment, and formative assessment. These contemporary approaches enable a more nuanced consideration of individual achievements and the progress of learners.*

Keywords: *research, Language, Assessment System, Innovation, Development, Methodology, pedagogical strategy, modern approach, online platform.*

In modern education, it is important to use new approaches, especially in teaching foreign languages. Modern methods of teaching foreign languages offer a variety of concepts, methods and technologies, both traditional and modern. Teachers choose approaches depending on the learning objectives, student characteristics, and other factors. Each method has its own strengths and weaknesses, and its effectiveness depends on the specific goals and learning conditions.¹

School education plays an important role in shaping the worldview of children. In today's society, information technology makes it easy to find answers to questions and receive expert advice. However, for the full development of a child, it is necessary to create conditions conducive to the realization of his inner potential. The school should provide such conditions for the comprehensive development of students' personality. Evaluation through project activities is becoming an increasingly popular alternative to traditional testing methods. This approach not only allows you to evaluate students' knowledge, but also develops their practical skills, critical thinking and creativity. Let's take a closer look at how project activities can be used in language teaching. Project design, creating an approach that will allow students to independently plan, develop and defend their individual projects in learning a foreign language. This will contribute to a more active involvement of students in communication.² This method was developed in the field of pedagogy in the early 20th century and was based on the pragmatic philosophy of John Dewey. John Dewey (1859-1952) — an American educator, psychologist, and philosopher — criticized the prevailing educational system in the United States at that time, which he considered dogmatic, abstract, and disconnected from real life. He advocated for the need to reform the educational system, asserting that knowledge

¹ М. В. Фоминых, Б. А. Ускова, Н. О. Ветлугина. (2024). Инновационные методы обучения иностранным языкам инновационные методы обучения иностранным языкам. Екатеринбург.

² Najmiddinova Gulnora Najmiddin qizi "The Integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into education system".34-37 b. Tamaddun Nuri ,ISSN 2181-8258,12-son (63) Ilmiy, ijtimoiy-falsafiy, madaniy-ma'rifiy, adabiy-badiiy jurnal,12.12.2024.

should be formed through students' independent practical activities and personal experiences. In various countries, the project method proposed by Dewey gained significant popularity due to its humanistic approach to education, which combines theoretical knowledge with its practical application to solve real problems in collaborative student activities.³ A key idea that highlights the relevance of the project method in modern education is: "Everything I learn, I know why I need it and how I can apply this knowledge." This approach attracts various educational systems seeking to find a reasonable balance between practical skills and academic knowledge.

Advantages of Project-Based Learning

1	Development of Critical Thinking	Students acquire skills in analyzing information, formulating conclusions, and making informed decisions.
2	Increased Motivation for Learning	Project work is often related to relevant and interesting topics, which enhances student engagement.
3	Formation of Practical Skills	Students have the opportunity to apply theoretical knowledge in practice, developing skills useful in life and professional activities
4	Collaboration and Teamwork	Project-based activities require interaction with other participants, fostering the development of communication skills and teamwork abilities.
5	Encouragement of Creativity and Innovative Thinking	Students have the opportunity to demonstrate creative approaches to problem-solving, promoting the development of creative thinking.

³ Nazarova Nurjahon Bakhodirovna "Olam lisoniy manzarasida mikrotoponimlarning o 'rni" //Международный журнал искусство слова. – 2023. – Т. 6. – №. 5.

6	In-Depth Understanding of the Subject	Working on a project allows for a deeper exploration of the chosen topic, contributing to better retention of educational material.
7	Development of Independence	Students learn to plan and organize their activities, which enhances their independence and sense of responsibility.
8	Preparation for Real-Life Situations	Project-based learning often simulates real tasks and challenges, helping students prepare for future obstacles.

In project training, it is important not only to achieve the final result, but also to pay attention to the process of working on the project itself.⁴ The assessment includes observing how students interact with each other, how they approach solving problems, and how they develop their ideas. For example, a teacher can observe the process of creating a video project assigned to the students. During the observation, it is important to consider how students discuss their ideas, assign roles, and jointly resolve emerging issues. The assessment may include observations of their communication and collaboration, not just the quality of the finished video.⁵

Assessment can take various forms and include both a formative and a summative assessment. A formative assessment is carried out during the course of the project, which gives students the opportunity to receive feedback and make changes to their work. Example: While working on a research project, students can receive interim feedback from a teacher about their research or presentations. For example, if a group has submitted a draft of their work, the teacher can make recommendations for improving the structure or content. This allows students to finalize the project to its final version, which will then be evaluated summatively. Thus, the emphasis on the learning process and multi-level assessment contribute to

⁴ Тихненко Галина Николаевна. (2017). Использование проектной методики в преподавании иностранного языка. Санкт – Петербург.

⁵ Najmiddinova Mehriqul Najmiddin qizi “Ingliz va o‘zbek tilida “mehmondo ‘stlik”ga oid maqollarning lingvokulturologik xususiyatlari”. 74 b. Tamaddun nuri / The light of civilization ISSN 2181-8258 2024-yil, 10-son (61) Ilmiy, ijtimoiy-falsafiy, madaniy-ma’rifiy, adabiy-badiiy jurnal. DOI: <https://jurnal.tamaddunnuri.uz/index.php/tmj/article/view/972>.

deeper learning of the material, as well as the development of cooperation and critical thinking skills among students.

In conclusion, project-based learning is a powerful and effective approach to learning that differs significantly from traditional methods.⁶ It not only deepens students' understanding of the learning material, but also develops key skills such as critical thinking, creativity, and teamwork. In today's world, where information is changing rapidly and professional competence requirements are increasing, the ability to apply knowledge in practice is becoming especially important. Project-based learning creates conditions for the active involvement of students in the educational process. It allows them not only to master theoretical concepts, but also to use them in real situations, which contributes to the formation of a deeper and more meaningful attitude to learning. In addition, working on projects develops skills of independence and responsibility, as students learn to plan their actions, set goals and achieve them. Nevertheless, despite all the advantages of project-based learning.

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